

UNIVERSITY OF
LINCOLN

**Promoting Diversity Using UK Corporate Governance Code 2018: A Comparative
Study of Listed and Non-Listed Supermarkets in The United Kingdom.**

Submitted in partial fulfilment of

MSc Governance

Iyabosola Yetunde OLUKOYA

25646861

Supervised by Senior Lecturer/Program Leader Nicola Wood

7th October 2022

11,530 words

Lincoln International Business School
University of Lincoln

ETHICS DECLARATION FORM

Having reviewed the ethical implications of this research, I certify that there are no issues requiring Ethical consideration from LEAS.

I certify that I am undertaking desk-based research, using secondary sources only which will be carried out in compliance with the University’s ethical guidelines for research, and with all other relevant University policies and procedures. If there are any changes to the research requiring ethical clearance, I shall gain approval from LEAS before continuing with the research. I have given my supervisor a full picture of the procedure I have followed so far and/or am committed to follow by signing this declaration.

The title of my dissertation:

PROMOTING DIVERSITY USING UK CORPORATE GOVERNANCE CODE 2018: A
.....
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LISTED AND NON-LISTED SUPERMARKETS IN THE
.....
UNITED KINGDOM.
.....

Name.: IYABOSOLA YETUNDE OLUKOYA
.....

Student ID: 25646861
.....

Signed: Iyabosola Yetunde Olukoya
.....

Date: 7th October 2022
.....

By signing and accepting these conditions your dissertation is granted ethical approval (ref: 2022_7740).

DECLARATION OF AUTHORSHIP

I declare that this dissertation is my work and that I have correctly acknowledged the work of others. This dissertation is in accordance with University and College guidance on good academic conduct (and how to avoid plagiarism and other assessment irregularities).

Signed: Iyabosola Yetunde OLUKOYA

Date: 7th October 2022

DEDICATION

To God Almighty the creator of heaven and earth

ABSTRACT

This study explores the promotion of diversity using the UK corporate governance code 2018 and makes a comparison of listed and non-listed supermarkets in the United Kingdom in the last four years. The samples drawn were from three listed and three non-listed supermarkets in relation to gender diversity on the board, gender pay gap, and diversity and inclusion among employees.

This study adopted the post-positivism paradigm, which generally involved the use of a quantitative mode of inquiry. The design adopted a comparative survey design for the study and data were collected from secondary sources mostly from financial reports, gender pay gap reports, websites, and press releases from the selected supermarkets. Six of the supermarkets (listed and non-listed) were from the available list of UK supermarkets using a stratified sampling technique. The study also adopted the use of statistics such as frequency, percentages, and charts for data analysis.

The result of the first research question revealed that the UK corporate governance code 2018 has not consistently promoted gender diversity among most supermarkets, although listed supermarkets showed better efforts in achieving gender diversity on the board than the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years. The result of the second research showed that the UK corporate governance code 2018 is effective in reducing gender pay gaps among listed supermarkets when compared to the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years. Finally, the UK corporate governance code 2018 promoted diversity among employees in listed supermarkets but remained inconsistent in its implementation in non-listed supermarkets in the last four years.

Overall, the study provides insight into how the recent UK code impacts the retail industry with a special focus on supermarkets.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, UK Corporate Governance Code 2018, Gender Diversity, Gender Pay Gap, Diversity, and Inclusion among Employees, Listed and Non-listed Supermarkets.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	
Ethical Declaration Form	ii
Declaration of Authorship	iii
Dedication	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Abstract	vi
Detailed Table of Content	vii
List of Tables	x
List of Figures	xi
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	xii
CHAPTER1: Introduction	1
Background.....	1
Problem Statement.....	3
1.3 Research Motivations.....	3
1.4 Aims and Objectives & Research Questions.....	4
1.4.1 Aims and Objectives.....	4
1.4.2 Research Questions	4
1.5 Research Contribution	4
CHAPTER 2: Literature Review	5
2.1 Background	5
2.1.1 UK Corporate Governance Code 2018.....	5
2.2 View of UK Corporate Code on Gender Diversity on the Board	5
2.3 Meaning of Gender Diversity on the Board.....	6
2.3.1 Gender Diversity on the Board: Research in UK Retail Industry	7
2.4. Gender Pay Gap	9
2.4.1 Meaning of Gender Pay Gap	9
2.4.2 Gender Pay Gap Calculations	10
2.4.3 Regulations on Gender Pay Gap.....	10
2.4.4 Gender Pay Gap Reporting	11
2.4.5 Research on Gender Pay Gap in the UK Retail Industry	11
2.5 Diversity & Inclusion among Employees	13
2.5.1 Meaning of Diversity and Inclusion	13

2.5.2 Laws and Regulations on Diversity & Inclusion	14
2.5.3 Research on Employee Gender Diversity in the UK Retail Industry	15
CHAPTER 3: Methodology	17
3.1 Introduction	17
3.2 Research Methodology.....	17
3.2.1 Philosophical Worldview	17
3.2.2 Quantitative Research	18
3.2.3 Justification of Quantitative Research	19
3.3 Research Design	19
3.3.1 Primary and Secondary Research.....	19
3.4. Data Collection	20
3.4.1 Sampling Design	20
3.4.2 List of most popular Supermarkets Chains	20
3.4.3 Sample Selection Process	21
3.4.4 Final Sample Selection	22
3.5 Time Horizon	22
3.6 Data Analysis	23
3.6.1 Unit of Analysis & Measurement	23
CHAPTER 4: Analyses & Discussion	24
4.0 Introduction	24
4.1 Analyses	24
4.1.1 Research Question One	24
4.1.2 Research Question Two	29
4.1.3 Research Question Three	33
4.2 Discussion of Findings	40
CHAPTER 5: Conclusion	42
5.0 Introduction.....	42
5.1. Summary of Findings	42
5.2 Contribution & Implication of Findings	42
5.3 Limitation of the Study.....	43
5.4 Suggestions for Future Research	43

References	44
Appendices	60

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1 Gender Diversity on the Board.....	60
Table 4.2 Gender Pay Gap (hourly pay gap)	61
Table 4.3 Gender diversity Among Employees.....	62

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1: World report on compliance with corporate governance in companies	2
Figure 4.1: Board Gender Diversity in Booths & Iceland	24
Figure 4.2: Board Gender Diversity in Lincolnshire Co-op	25
Figure 4.3: Board Gender Diversity in ASDA Plc	26
Figure 4.4: Board Gender Diversity in Sainsbury's Plc	27
Figure 4.5: Board Gender Diversity in Tesco Plc	28
Figure 4.6: Mean Gender Pay Gap in Booths	29
Figure 4.7: Mean Gender Pay Gap in Iceland	30
Figure 4.8: Mean Gender Pay Gap in Lincolnshire Co-op	30
Figure 4.9: Mean Gender Pay Gap in ASDA Plc	31
Figure 4.10: Mean Gender Pay Gap in Sainsbury's Plc	31
Figure 4.11: Mean Gender Pay Gap in Tesco Plc	32
Figure 4.12: Gender Diversity among Employees in Booths	33
Figure 4.13: Gender Diversity among Employees in Iceland	34
Figure 4.14: Gender Diversity among Employees in Lincolnshire Co-op	35
Figure 4.15: Gender Diversity among Employees in ASDA Plc	36
Figure 4.16: Gender Diversity among Employees in Sainsbury's Plc	37
Figure 4.17: Gender Diversity among Employees in Tesco Plc.....	38

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

D&I – Diversity and Inclusion

FRC – Financial Reporting Council

UK – United Kingdom

UK Code – United Kingdom Corporate Governance Code 2018

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Corporate governance code is a compliance tool established to specify the mode of operation of businesses around the world. The corporate governance structure in every organization reflects the distribution of rights and responsibilities among different stakeholders within the organization, rules, and procedures for making decisions on corporate affairs (ALHarbi, 2018). Corporate governance is how a corporation is structured, regulated, managed, and operated. It essentially balances the interests of a company's many stakeholders, such as management, shareholders, suppliers, financiers, customers, government, and the community (Vintila & Moscu, 2015; Bhandari, 2018).

Over the years, many corporate failures and the collapse of well-established companies have forced politicians, and regulators to review and establish new ways of improving corporate governance. Corporate failures and financial scandals fuelled the development of corporate governance in the United Kingdom (Mallin, 2019). Significant occurrences leading to corporate scandals like the collapse of many high-profile corporations such as Enron, Satyam & Wells Fargo, and the financial crisis of 2007 highlighted the need for stricter corporate governance codes to ensure transparency, and accountability and address other corporate issues such as extravagant compensation received by company executives, appointment and re-appointment of the board of directors, focus on short-term profitability at the expense of shareholders' expectations (L'Huillier, 2014; Sanni, 2015; Vintila & Moscu, 2015; Avcin & Balcioglu, 2017; ALHarbi, 2018).

The first edition of the UK Corporate Governance Code was issued in 1992 by the Cadbury Committee following various scandals and collapses, Colloroll and Polly Peck to mention a few, as well as a lack of trust in many UK companies as regards financial reporting (Mallin, 2019). It has been amended multiple times over the years. The recent UK Corporate Governance Code was published in 2018, which focuses on the importance and value of corporate culture in fostering trust in business and facilitating meaningful engagement with the company's stakeholders and wider society (Mallin, 2019). The Code also considered new requirements for the board to consider such as diversity on the board and the needs and views of wider stakeholders; hence, the need for diversity and inclusion in business (Financial Reporting Council, 2018).

Diversity cuts across the board, gender pay gap, diversity, and inclusion in the workforce. Board diversity seeks to foster a wide range of demographic traits and qualities in the boardroom (ACCA, 2018). Diversity in the workplace has been centred on gender, but it has grown over time to incorporate more factors that must exist in the workplace, which is in the stakeholders’ interest (Hosny and Elgharbavy, 2021). In the UK retail market, the topic of diversity and inclusion (D&I) has evolved considerably over the last decade. The focus is on improving the representation of women, and ethnic minorities and breaching pay gaps among gender groups in the organizations. Recently, there has been a shift towards inclusion with the understanding that inclusion not only leads to diversity but also drives meaningful positive change that can be sustained in the long term (MBS Intelligence, 2021). However, recent reports on diversity in industries globally have given room for concern on how corporations operate in their industries despite the implementation of corporate governance and other regulations in firms. According to (Equileap, 2022), the implementation of corporate governance code globally is stated in figure 1.1:

Figure 1.1: World Report on compliance with corporate governance code in companies

(Equileap,2022)

The figure reflects the global picture of how companies complied with the corporate governance code concerning board diversity, workforce diversity, and the gender pay gap. From the data, 26% of companies show board diversity, 37% of companies show workforce diversity, and 0.5% of companies show equal gender pay. This is contrary to the obligations of companies

to meet the Hampton-Alexander threshold (33% female board representation) and equal gender pay.

This reflects a serious problem with the efficacy of the corporate governance code, forming the basis for investigating companies' compliance with the UK corporate governance code to ascertain their level of compliance.

1.2 Problem Statement

Corporate governance code is a compliance tool established to specify the mode of operation of businesses around the world. Globally, the implementation of corporate governance has given room for concern about how corporations operate in their industries. According to the report given in 2022 by Equileap, (2022), the results showed that 26% of companies show board diversity, 37% of companies show workforce diversity, and 0.5% of companies show equal gender pay. This is contrary to the obligations of the company to meet the Hampton-Alexander threshold (33% female board representation) and equal gender pay.

This form the basis for investigating companies' compliance with the UK corporate governance code because there is a need to establish the impact of the UK corporate governance code of 2018 on companies in the retail industry (supermarkets), showing the efficacy of how UK corporate governance code of 2018 promotes diversity, especially among listed and non-listed supermarkets in the United Kingdom.

1.3 Research Motivation

The UK corporate governance code was revised in 2018 and it has been the compliance code for the past 4 years (UK corporate governance code, 2018). Recently, there has been concern about how companies operate, how diverse their structures are (both at the board and senior management positions), operations, and treatment of staff at all levels. Based on this information, there is a need to ascertain the implementation and impact of the recent version of the 2018 code, among listed and non-listed supermarkets.

Many companies operate in their existing markets and industries using corporate governance codes as enacted in different countries. However, there is a concern globally about how companies operate, and how diverse their structures, operations, and treatment of staff are in all categories. This led to many countries making adjustments in their corporate governance codes to reflect best practices in companies' operations in their respective regions. Based on this information, there is a need to ascertain the impact of the recent version of the UK corporate

governance code, especially among supermarkets in the UK. Also, a comparison will be made between listed and non-listed supermarkets on how they implement the recent version of the UK corporate governance code.

1.4 Aims, Objectives, and Research Questions

1.4.1 Aims and Objectives

The aim and objectives of the study are to ascertain how the 2018 UK corporate governance code promotes diversity among listed and non-listed supermarkets in the United Kingdom. Specifically, this study seeks to:

- a. Determine whether the 2018 UK corporate governance code promotes gender diversity on the board between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the last four years.
- b. Compare how UK corporate governance code promotes diversity regarding the gender pay gap between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the last four years.
- c. Determine whether UK corporate governance code promotes gender diversity among employees between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the last four years.

1.4.2 Research Questions

To carry out the study, the following questions will be investigated:

- a. Has the UK corporate governance code promoted gender diversity on the board between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the last four years?
- b. Has the UK corporate governance promoted the gender pay gap among listed and non-listed supermarkets when compared to in the last four years?
- c. Has the UK corporate governance code promoted gender diversity among employees between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the last four years?

1.5 Research Contribution

The research seeks to ascertain the impact of the recent version of the UK corporate governance code on diversity among supermarkets in the UK. This will significantly add to the existing literature on the UK corporate governance code because there is a paucity of studies in this area. Also, focusing on supermarket businesses in the UK and how the UK corporate governance code has been complied with, this investigation will provide a novel dimension to the study and adds to the existing literature. Finally, the comparison made between listed and non-listed supermarkets on how UK 2018 code promotes diversity will provide a novel dimension to the study and add to the existing literature.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Background

2.1.1 UK Corporate Governance Code 2018

The UK Corporate Governance Code also known as (the code) was published by the Financial Reporting Council in 2018. It was published to set up standards for listed companies on the London Stock Exchange, such standards include board leadership and purpose, board composition, remuneration, nomination and audit committees, and shareholder relations (Mallin, 2019). All listed companies on the London Stock Exchange must apply the principles of the Code and comply with it. The code also considered new requirements for companies' operations such as board diversity, diversity and inclusion, corporate culture, needs, and views of a wide range of stakeholders (UK Corporate Governance Code, 2018). Corporate governance in the UK is guided by various codes that encompass policies, laws, and customs on how the nation conducts its business. The UK's corporate governance code serves as a check on the powers and authority that are wielded by corporate directors. The foundations of corporate governance are deemed to be accountability, transparency, independence, and fairness (Hampton & Alexander, 2016 & ALHarbi, 2018).

At the heart of this Code is an updated set of principles that emphasize the value of good corporate governance for long-term sustainable success. By applying the Principles, following the more detailed Provisions, and using the associated guidance, companies can demonstrate throughout their reporting how the governance of the company contributes to its long-term sustainable success and achieve wider objectives (Vintila & Moscu, 2015; Avcin & Balcioglu, 2017; Financial Reporting Council, 2018).

2.2 View of The UK Corporate Governance Code 2018 on Gender Diversity on The Board

According to Principle J of the UK corporate governance code,

‘Appointments to the board should be subject to a thorough, rigorous, and transparent method, and an effective succession plan for the board and senior management should be maintained. Both nominations and succession plans should be based on merit and objective criteria, and should promote gender, social and ethnic diversity, cognitive and personal qualities.’ (UK Corporate Governance Code, 2018).

Principle L of the UK code states that:

‘The board should be evaluated annually with regards to its composition and diversity, and how well members of the board collaborate to achieve their goals. Each director’s performance will be evaluated individually to show if they are still making a valuable contribution.’ (UK Corporate Governance Code, 2018).

Provision 23 (c and d) of the Code also states that:

‘The annual report should state the policy on diversity and inclusion, how objectives are linked to the company’s strategy, the implementation and progress made so far, and detailed reports on the gender balance of senior management.’ (UK Corporate Governance Code, 2018).

From the above, the 2018 UK code has demanded that diversity should be considered during appointments, succession to the board, and at the senior management level. It also stipulated that during the evaluation of the board diversity should be highly considered. Also, the annual report of each listing company should give detailed reports on its implementation of diversity and inclusion and gender balance at the senior management level.

2.3 Meaning of Gender Diversity on The Board

According to Carter et al., (2003), board gender diversity is a key component of corporate governance. It is defined as the proportion of female directors on a company’s board of directors. There are two types of board diversity according to Kang et al. (2007), observable diversity and less visible diversity. Observable diversity includes race/nationality, ethnic background, gender, and age. Less visible diversity on the hand, includes differences in industry experience, education, functional and vocational background, and organizational membership. Board diversity according to Goyal et al., (2019) involves the distribution of diverse traits and qualities among directors which influence their attitudes and perspectives, as well as the changes in the composition of the boards. Diverse boards are believed to be more effective in performing their roles and are usually suggested by a variety of internal and external stakeholders (Randoy and Oxelheim, 2006). It is the view of ACCA, (2018) that board diversity seeks to foster a wide range of demographic traits and qualities in the boardroom.

Gender diversity has become a major issue for practically all companies as the number of employees has increased significantly (Sener and Karaye, 2014). Over the last decades, organisations have come under increasing regulatory and social pressure to support gender-board diversity (Biswas et al.,2021). To increase the effort of gender equity, numerous

governments have introduced gender quotas on corporate boards since 2003 (Goyal et al., 2019). At all levels of management as well as among employees, gender diversity is crucial to provide a diverse environment within the organisation, better outcomes for customers, better business returns, greater innovation, and new ideas, more attractiveness to employees, and improved reputation and brand (PWC, 2021). As a result of the failure of big companies such as Enron, Lehman Brothers, and WorldCom, there is more agitation for corporate governance compliance (Sener and Kararye, 2014). For both moral and financial reasons, institutional investors, policy advocates, and the public have campaigned for more female participation and equity in corporate governance (Carter et al., 2003).

From another perspective which focuses on the impact of women's board representation, gender diversity and the presence of women on the board of directors could be considered good indicators of social responsibility because the rejection of gender diversity on the board reflects symptoms of poor corporate governance (Nuria, Joaquina & Pilar, 2011). Different regulators, policymakers, and scholars emphasised the efficacy and merits of women's participation on the boards as significant characteristics of corporate board composition. Female board members perform monitoring functions more diligently than male board members; offer varieties of viewpoints and experiences to the board, which helps to improve the quality of board decisions (Adams & Ferreira 2009; Arvanitis, Evangelos & George, 2022).

The presence of female board members on corporate boards have been found to enhance and improve the ability of such board to exercise control and play strategic roles in management decisions. Increased diversity would translate to the expansion of the pool of knowledge used to make improved group decisions, innovation, and creativity (Adams & Ferreira 2009; Garcia-Meca & Santana-Martín, 2022). According to Faccio, Marchica, and Mura (2016), Garcia-Meca and Santana-Martín (2022), women are less likely to take an excess risk when strategic decisions are made when compared to their male counterparts, which makes them more reliable when they take ethical and socially responsible decisions. In addition, female directors adopt a more interactive and participatory style when compared to male directors (Garcia-Meca & Santana-Martín, 2022). Therefore, women can enhance a firm's ability to be flexible and address ambiguity (Garcia-Meca & Santana-Martín, 2022).

2.3.1 Gender Diversity on The Board: Research in UK Retail Industry

The regulation on the promotion of board diversity based on the code encourages diversity and inclusion, without bias in an organization. Globally, women are estimated to have lower

chances of being employed than men and are more likely to be at the bottom of the professional ladder (Sealy, 2018; ILO, 2019; ILO, 2022; Zhu, 2021). In the UK market, the case for diversity is strong in the retail industry where the customer reigns supreme. The priorities include strengthening the diversity of leadership, inclusiveness of the working environment, and ensuring that products and services cater to Britain's highly diverse customer base (BRC, PwC & MBS Group, 2021). Reflecting on studies and reports around the UK retail industry, several studies have been carried out, reporting on the state of board diversities among companies in the retail industry across several sectors of the economy.

The report by Sealy, (2018) revealed that considerable progress has been made in increasing the diversity of UK boards since Lord Davies published his report on the gender balance of FTSE 100 boards in 2011. In 2017, women made up 27.7% on average of FTSE 100 boards, up from 12.5% in 2010, demonstrating continued progress towards the target of 33% by 2020, set by the follow-up Hampton-Alexander Review published in November 2016. This had reached 29.0% by July 2018. Progress in increasing the number of women in the top tier of FTSE 100 executive management has been slower. Women accounted for an average of just 19% of the members of the executive team in FTSE 100 companies in 2017, up from 12% in 2011. The Hampton-Alexander Review identified that further progress requires building diversity into the executive pipeline and recommended action by nomination committees to support this. The report showed that diversity is improving compared to previous years but has not reached the threshold by the Hampton-Alexander review.

(DLA Piper and Green Park, 2019) carried out a study on the diversity composition of leading retail boards across the UK, US, and Europe. It focused on two levels of leadership: the executive committees and the main boards (including Chairs). Focusing on the UK retail sector, an analysis of the gender and ethnic cultural diversity of the 10,000 leadership roles in the FTSE 100 showed a mixed picture for the largest retail companies publicly quoted on the London Stock Exchange. Retail had the highest number of top 20 female executives of all sectors analysed for the Green Park Leadership 10,000 report 2018. The pipeline of female leaders in the retail Top 100 is one of the highest, along with media (44.5%).

Similarly, (MBS, IGD, and PWC,2019) reported the state of diversity in the food and grocery industry. On gender diversity in the board, an average of 27.6% of board roles are occupied by women. At the executive committee level, this drops to 22.2%, while 35.9% of Direct Reports (into the Executive Committee) are women. Compared with the latest Hampton-

Alexander Review figures, food and grocery are ahead of the FTSE 350 cross-industry average at the Executive Committee and Direct Reports levels, but the sector is unlikely to reach the Hampton-Alexander target of 33% women by the end of 2020.

(BRC, PwC & MBS Group,2021) carried out in-depth research and analysis on diversity and inclusion in UK retail industry. They concluded that UK retail industry is close to achieving the Hampton-Alexander target (of 33% women on boards). Results showed that 37.5% of direct reports to the board are women, while 20% of retailers have their boards all males. Looking into sub-sectors, progress has also been made depending on the nature of the business. In fashion retail for, example, 51% of direct reports to the board are women. Progress is slower at the board level because 25% of seats are held by women; however, the high levels of representation on the executive committee and within the direct reports demonstrate that there is a strong pipeline of female talent which will eventually rise into board positions.

(Equileap,2022) reported that women comprise 35% of UK boards on average and 11% of the Chairperson positions (board of directors) in FTSE 250 companies. Also, women make up 30% of the management team and 39% of the total workforce.

Similarly, (Irvine et al.,2022), revealed that the final review (Hampton-Alexander Review) published in 2021 found that 250 and 350 FTSE companies had reached the target of having 33% representation of women on their boards. Across all FTSE 350 board members, 34.3% were women.

The retail industry is improving its board diversity status to surpass the recommendation of the Hampton-Alexander Review of 33%; however, the overall sight is the attainment of 50% gender diversity. Compared to the previous years, the code is working but at a gradual rate.

2.4 Gender Pay Gap

2.4.1 Meaning of Gender Pay Gap

The gender pay gap according to (Gov.UK, 2020) is defined as the disparity between the average income (mean or median) of men and women in a workforce. It is therefore calculated by dividing the average pay for women by a percentage of men's pay. The difference between the above-mentioned and 100% is the pay disparity. For instance, if women are paid 85%of what men are paid, the gender pay gap is 15% (Leaker, 2008).

Over the years, the gender pay gap has been an issue of discourse for all stakeholders because it affects every labour force in all sectors of the economy. Equal pay means that men and women, or employees of different ethnic backgrounds in the same employment performing the same jobs, similar jobs, or work of equal value receive equal pay, as set out in the Equality Act 2010 (Gantner, 2020; CDC, 2021). Although women tend to be overrepresented in sectors and jobs that pay less, the gender pay gap is a product of numerous and interconnected factors including gender stereotypes in education and the labour market, imbalances in caring and household responsibilities between women and men (ITUC, 2018; Miller et al., 2018 & Gantner, 2020).

2.4.2 Gender Pay Calculations

The gender pay gap is the difference between the average hourly earnings of men and that of women across an organisation, irrespective of their duties and portfolio. The gender pay gap calculations are a tool and measure for analysing pay gap issues in different workplaces. According to McElhaney and Smith, (2017), Brynin,(2017), Miller et al.,(2018), and Moyser,(2019), there are two categories of gender pay gap which are the mean and median pay gap. The mean gender pay gap is the difference between the average pay of men and women while the median is the midpoint of each gender group (the difference between the midpoints of each gender group). In the study, the mean gender pay gap was considered for analysis purposes and it is calculated as:

$$\text{Gender pay (wage) ratio} = \frac{\text{men's average earning} - \text{women's average earning}}{\text{men's average earning}} \times 100$$

2.4.3 Regulations on Gender Pay Gap

In the UK, companies with 250 or more employees need to report how large the pay gap is between their male and female employees. Regulations and legislation are guiding the implementation of the gender pay gap in the UK. The first is the Equal Pay Act was introduced in 1970 and makes it illegal to pay a woman less than a man for the same work (Colebrook, Snelling & Longlands, 2018).

Afterward, the Equality Act of 2010 was established to provide transparency and solution to equal pay problems in the UK. In 2018, Regulations 2017 required its operation to be extended to cover private and third-sector employers with 250 or more employees to report information such as mean and median gender pay gap figures, the gender gap in bonus earnings, the proportion of men and women receiving bonuses, and the proportion of men and women in

each pay quartile (Colebrook, Snelling & Longlands, 2018; PWC, 2021; Close The Gap Working Paper, 2022).

2.4.4 Gender Pay Gap Reporting

In 2017, the United Kingdom government passed a law requiring that all companies with more than 250 employees in all sectors report six gender pay gap figures regularly, with the majority including voluntary explanatory reports (Brown, 2019). According to (Gov. UK, 2020), companies with 250 employees or more must comply with the gender pay gap reporting. Large employers are required by law to provide information about the gender pay gap both on their websites and the UK government website (Brown, 2019).

2.4.5 Research on Gender Pay Gap in The UK Retail Industry

The gender pay gap has a long history (National Union Education, 2019) and has been an issue of discourse for all stakeholders because it affects every labour force in all sectors of the economy. In the UK, several studies have been conducted and reports made to reveal the state of gender gap pay in the market and retail industry.

(Brynin,2017) carried out research to explore the gender pay gap which focused on data from the Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings. The findings revealed a median gender pay gap for 18.1% of full and part-time workers in 2016. The gap for full-time employees only was smaller at 9.4%. While part-time women tended to earn slightly more than part-time men (6%), part-time women earned 36.5% less than full-time men. From the angle of the economic sector, the gender pay gap is larger in the private sector, at £3.11 per hour over the period 1993-2014, than in the public sector where the gap is £2.38 per hour (adjusted for inflation). The pay gap between male and female graduates in the public sector is comparatively small (£1.63 per hour) but higher in the private sector (£2.77 per hour), suggesting that female graduates in the private sector gain less from their education in terms of parity with men. Similarly, (Colebrook et al.,2018) analysed the gender pay gap in the UK using data published through the Office for National Statistics Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings (ONS ASHE).

The report showed that the UK has a gender pay gap of 18.4% i.e., women earn an average of 18.4% more than men. The pay gap is 9.1% for full-time work and -5.1% for part-time work. Part-time jobs contribute more to the overall pay because women account for three-quarters of the part-time workforce and it pays less per hour than full-time work, on average. Also, the pay

gap is caused by six drivers such as occupational segregation (more men than women working in certain higher-paid occupations); seniority (women tend to be in less senior roles than men); the maternity penalty; the lower level of part-time pay; historical skills gap between men and women; and discrimination and bias.

(Jewell et al.,2018) carried out a study on the UK gender pay gap, which involved a large, longitudinal, representative, and employer-employee-linked dataset from 2002-2016. Results showed that men's average hourly wage was 25% higher than women's average hourly wage in this period. Also, the allocation of men and women over occupations contributed a similarly small amount to the gender wage gap. Retail and hospitality services were the only broad industry group where women were to any great extent disproportionately employed by low-wage firms, compared with the men working in the same industry. Also, CDC, (2021) reported on the gender and ethnicity pay gap report regarding their institution. Results showed that between 2019 and 2020, the mean gender pay gap increased from 29% to 30%; the median increased from 28% to 31%. The gender bonus mean gap also increased from 17% to 32% while the median bonus gap was 52%. From the report, it was disappointing that the pay gap has not narrowed in the UK especially when female leadership in the UK (directors and above) increased.

Furthermore, White, (2021) reported on the gender pay gap in 2021 by working with the Office for National Statistics. The gender pay gap reporting is a long time series, calculated from the Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings (ASHE) which samples all employee jobs in all sizes of companies. Results showed that in 2021, the gap among full-time employees was 7.9% (increased from 7.0% in 2020). Among all employees, the gender pay gap is 15.4% (increased from 14.9% in 2022). The gender pay gap has been declining slowly over time; over the last decade, it has fallen by approximately a quarter among both full-time employees and all employees.

According to the (British Council,2021), the pay gap observed is 17.7%. In the reporting year 2019/20, the proportion of women in the top quartile of earners was 45.8% (increased from 43.5%) which contributed to narrowing the pay gaps while the proportion of women in the bottom quartile of earners increased from 67.9% to 71% which, on its own would have caused the pay gaps to grow.

Similarly, (Abid,2021) presented a report on the gender pay gap on behalf of the UK Women's Budget Group in the UK. Drawing data from the Office for National Statistics,

Annual Survey of Hours, and Earnings (ASHE), the gender pay gap on an hourly basis for all employees is 15.4% (either full-time or part-time).

Finally, (Irvine et al.,2022) provided an analysis of women's participation in the labour market and business across the UK. Results showed that the gender pay gap in median hourly pay (excluding overtime) between men and women was 15.4% for all employees.

From the literature, the gender pay gap tends to be lower when pay itself is lower. The gender pay gap has narrowed over time, but that progress looks to have stalled due to reasons. More women work in lower-paid jobs and part-time jobs which makes their pay lower. The UK corporate governance code is working but at a slower rate. More needs to be done to mentor female individuals to embrace executive jobs and high pay jobs. This study focused on establishing the frontier of knowledge by focusing on the supermarket industry, which is a novel area of investigation.

2.5 Diversity and Inclusion Among Employees

2.5.1 Meaning of Diversity and Inclusion

The concept of diversity and inclusion are important variables in every organization that wants to improve performance and sustain its operation over time since regulations have been established to encourage diversity in workplaces. Diversity and inclusion are frequently used interchangeably, yet they are different ideas that contribute to the equity balance in an organization (Moore et al., 2020, 1042). Diversity involves having a variety of employees with different backgrounds, perspectives, and life experiences such as race, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation, religion, disability, or veteran status (Urwin et al, 2013; Rohwerder, 2017; ILO, 2020; Zhu, 2021; Dynata, 2021).

On the other hand, inclusion refers to all efforts made to help all employees feel involved, valued, respected, treated fairly, and have a sense of belonging in any organization (Dynata,2021). Inclusion occurs when people's differences are valued and utilized for everyone to succeed at work (CIPD, 2021). An inclusive workplace is one in which everyone feels like they belong without having to conform, that their contribution is valued, and that they may perform to full capacity, regardless of their background, identity, or circumstances (CIPD, 2021).

There is a discourse around diversity and inclusion in industries because several questions have been made on why the chance to succeed is within a group of a favoured few. While the

case for diversity and inclusion is strong in all business sectors, it is especially so in an industry like food and grocery, where customers' choices and reigns are supreme (MBS, IGD & PWC, 2019). In the UK, the retail industry is a dynamic and innovative industry that attracted different categories of employees. Recently, attention has been focused on inclusion because it leads to diversity and drives meaningful positive change that can be sustained in the long term (BRC, PwC & MBS Group, 2021).

As the retail consumer landscape evolves, diverse communities represent a larger and more important part of total buying power. There is huge competition for customers and market share, which means the leadership teams that set direction and strategy for retail brands need to understand the widest possible patterns of buying behaviours and motivations. A changing consumer and retail environment combined with greater regulation and activism in matters of social and political importance proves there is a strong business, moral and regulatory case for greater diversity in senior leadership (DLA Piper & Green Park, 2019; BRC, PwC & MBS Group, 2021). Finally, the consistent demand of the government for gender and ethnicity reporting on equal pay and representation in the UK is additional pressure for change. Transparent reporting exposes inequalities between employee groups and has a significant impact on organizations' reputations (DLA Piper & Green Park, 2019; Chaudhry et al., 2021).

2.5.2 Laws & Regulations on Diversity and Inclusion

The origin of diversity in the workplace started and developed in the United States during the 1980s and spread in the 1990s to other western economies (Brazzel, 2003 as cited in ILO, 2022). Some organizations were set up to promote diversity and inclusion over time. An example is the International Labour Organization (ILO) which promotes decent and productive work for women and men in conditions of freedom, dignity, economic security, and equal opportunity. The ILO strives to promote more inclusive workplaces and address discrimination on all grounds, notably gender, ethnicity, race, indigenous status, disability, HIV status, sexual orientation, and gender identity, by ensuring equal opportunities and treatment at work. Generally, all UN member States agreed to the principle of equal opportunities at work for all and ending discrimination at work is a core ILO standard (ILO, 2022).

In the UK, there are several standards like BSI (BSI 76000 Valuing People), ISO human resource management suite (ISO 9001 Quality Management), and Investors in People (IIP) that provide rules and guidelines to help organizations recognize the actual and potential value of their workforce, ensure policies and working practices are bias-free (CIPD, 2021). Also, the

UK Equality Act of 2010 is another regulation, and it notes ten protected characteristics such as age; disability; marriage or civil partnership; sex; sexuality; gender reassignment; pregnancy and maternity; race, religion, or belief; and age (Cassell, et al., 2022).

2.5.3 Research on employee Gender Diversity in The UK Retail Industry

Diversity and inclusion among the employees in the UK market is an interesting focus because there is still a long way to go in focusing on this area. This is also diverse depending on the type of business and products offered for sale in the retail market. In the report of (BRC, PwC & MBS Group, 2021), they concluded that the UK retail industry reflects the gender diversity in the workforce that is highly affected by the company's brand and product offering. Retailers whose products are predominantly marketed towards men have fewer women in their workforces than those with women as primary customers. Also, looking into various sub-sectors, the female representation in the retail workforce had an average of 64%, ranging from 30% at a technology retailer to 97% at a women's clothing brand. In fashion retail, women were up to 78% of the workforce. Generally, Equileap,(2022) report revealed that women comprise 39% of the total workforce in UK firms.

According to Irvine et al., (2022), 15.52 million women aged 16 and above were in employment from October to December 2021 in the UK. The female employment rate was 72.2% (a decrease from 72.7% between December 2019 to February 2020) while the male employment rate was 78.8%. 9.68 million women were working full-time, while 5.84 million were working part-time. Most part-time employment was by women (38%), compared to 13% of men. The most common sectors for women's employment in the UK are health and social work (accounting for 21% of all jobs held by women as of September 2021), the wholesale and retail trade (13%), and education (12%). In the health and social work sector, 78% of jobs are held by women and in education, it is 70%. Comparing employment by industry in the UK, the sectors with the most women in employment are health and social work (accounting for 21% of all jobs held by women as of September 2021), wholesale and retail trade (13%), and education (12%). For men, the most common sectors also included the wholesale and retail trade (14% of all jobs held by men), followed by manufacturing and construction (both 10%). 78% of jobs in the health and social work sector and 70% of jobs in education are held by women. Sectors, where only a small proportion of jobs are held by women, include construction (15%), mining and quarrying (17%), and transportation and storage (23%). In the UK retail industry, studies conducted are few and this study seeks to expand the frontier of knowledge by focusing on supermarkets.

The literature reviewed showed there is an engagement gap in the firms which reduces the attainment of inclusion in any company. Hence, this study seeks to focus on supermarkets to ascertain the state of diversity and inclusion in the industry.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology used for investigation in this study. This includes the adoption of a post-positivism paradigm and comparative survey design as research methodology and design respectively. The data collection process, sampling design, and sample selection process are discussed; data analysis including the unit of analysis and measurement are presented.

3.2 Research Methodology

(Thomas & Nelson, 2001) defined research methodology as a systematic process of active inquiry and discovery through collecting, analysing, and inferring from data so that we can understand a given phenomenon in which we are interested. It involves using a scientific process and a systematic procedure of collecting, organizing, analysing, and summarizing information about a phenomenon for knowledge. It is a scientific mode of inquiry aimed at proving an explanation and understanding of a phenomenon.

3.2.1 Philosophical Worldview:

Making scientific inquiry would involve several world view or paradigm, which directs how data is collected for research purpose since it still influences the practice of research. This includes the post-positivism, constructivism, and pragmatism paradigms (Bryman, 2012; Creswell, 2014). The post-positivist assumptions have represented the traditional form of research, and these assumptions hold more for quantitative research. According to (Phillips and Burbules, 2000) as cited by (Creswell, 2014), objectivity is an important characteristic that provides good inquiry because it does not give room for biases in the post-positivism paradigm. It recognizes research as the process of making claims, refining, or refuting claims and most quantitative research starts with the test of a theory. Finally, the collection of data, evidence, and rational considerations shape knowledge and defines cause-and-effect relationships. For constructivism paradigm, it is associated with qualitative research where human beings are allowed to construct meanings as they engage with the world they are interpreting (Thomas & Nelson, 2001; Creswell, 2014). Furthermore, qualitative researchers tend to use open-ended questions so that the participants can share their views; while the combination of the properties of both paradigms in a single study is the transformative paradigm (Bryman, 2012; Creswell, 2014).

This study prefers and will adopt the post-positivism paradigm, which generally involves the use of a quantitative mode of inquiry. The post-positivism paradigm is an epistemological position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond (Bryman, 2012). Post-positivism paradigm allows the generation of knowledge through the gathering of facts using a deductive approach. Post-positivists hold a deterministic philosophy whereby the problems studied by post-positivists reflect the need to identify and assess the causes that influence outcomes (Creswell, 2014). The knowledge derived through the post-positivist approach is based on careful observation and measurement of the objective reality that exists. Thus, developing numeric measures of observations and studying the behaviour of individuals becomes paramount for a post-positivist paradigm (Creswell, 2014).

3.2.2 Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is a mode of inquiry that requires the use of a quality measure with good psychometric properties (standardized instruments) so that the varying perspective and experiences of people can fit into a limited number of predetermined response categories to which numbers are assigned. This is because it is possible to measure the reactions of many people using a limited set of questions, facilitating comparison and statistical aggregation of the data for sound generalization (Patton, 1990; Robson & McCartan, 2016). Furthermore, it involves the collection of numeric data to provide discrete information for reaching an unbiased conclusion about a study. It collects numeric data as exhibiting a view of the relationship between theory and research as deductive and a predilection for a natural science approach, and as having an objective conception of social realities (Bryman, 2012). Quantitative research is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. It is an approach where measurement and quantification are central to its operation; accuracy and precision of measurement are sought, which does not allow room for being biased (Robson & McCartan, 2016). Furthermore, it involves the collection of numeric data to provide discrete information for reaching an unbiased conclusion about a study. It collects numeric data as exhibiting a view of the relationship between theory and research as deductive and a predilection for a natural science approach and having an objective conception of social realities (Bryman, 2012). Quantitative research is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. It is an approach where measurement and quantification are central to its operation; accuracy and precision of measurement are sought, which does not allow room for being biased (Robson & McCartan, 2016).

3.2.3 Justification of Quantitative Research

The use of quantitative research in this study is preferred because the data to be collected based on the research questions will be measured in numeric form. The level of objectivity is high, which eradicated every possibility of biases. Numeric data will be collected to provide discrete information for reaching an unbiased conclusion about the study. The data will incorporate how the UK corporate governance code 2018 impacts the operation of both listed and non-listed supermarkets in terms of gender diversity on the board, gender pay gap, diversity, and inclusion of employees and will be in numeric form, which fits quantitative research.

3.3 Research Design

Research design is a blueprint that defines the conditions for data collection and implementation of research or study. The design adopted for the study is the comparative survey design. Comparative research design is a survey design that seeks to provide explanations for similarities and differences to gain a greater awareness and a deeper understanding of social reality in different national contexts (Bryman, 2012). This type of survey design involves comparing a variable of study based on established groups, which implies that we can understand social phenomena better when they are compared to two or more meaningfully contrasting cases or situations (Bryman, 2012; Creswell, 2014). Comparative design is survey research in which there is a direct comparison between two or more cases, as in cross-cultural research (Bryman, 2012). In tracking the impact of the recent UK corporate governance code on the operation of both listed and non-listed supermarkets in the UK, a comparative research design will provide a suitable blueprint for the study.

3.3.1 Primary and Secondary Research

Using the primary source of data involves collecting data on the field of study from the information provider while the secondary source involves the collection of data from a third party other than the information provider. According to Jones et al., (2010) as cited by (Bryman, 2012), in primary data analysis, the researcher is responsible for collecting primary data (in raw form) from the information provider and conducting the analysis. This involves collecting primary data which focuses on the purposeful collection of new data from original sources, unlike secondary data whereby data is collected from a third party (usually in processed form).

In this study, data will be collected from secondary sources mostly from the financial statements, gender pay gap reports, websites, and press releases of the selected supermarkets. This is because the respondents involved in primary data collection purposes are not easily

assessable. Quantitative data on gender diversity on the board, gender pay gap, and diversity among employees was collected from the selected data sources of the selected supermarkets.

3.4 Data Collection

This study will adopt the primary data collection approach to obtain data needed for the investigation from six supermarkets in the UK. Data on gender diversity on the board, gender pay gap, diversity, and inclusion among employees will be collected from 6 selected supermarkets.

3.4.1 Sampling Design

The selection of the sample involves drawing a small group that adequately represents the population to conveniently collect data and generalize findings and reach conclusion. In this study, the sample study involves selecting an aggregate of six (6) UK supermarkets from the available list of UK supermarkets. There are thirty-eight (38) listed and non-listed supermarkets operating in the UK and their names are listed as follows:

3.4.2 List of most popular Supermarket chains (Q2, 2022)

	UK Supermarkets	London stock exchange status
1.	Abel and Cole	Private (not listed)
2.	Aldi	Private (not listed)
3.	Best one	Private (not listed)
4.	Booths	Private (not listed)
5.	Budgens	Private (not listed)
6.	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	Private (not listed)
7.	Costco	Private (not listed)
8.	Costcutter	Private (not listed)
9.	Farm-foods	Private (not listed)
10.	Gusto	Private (not listed)
11.	Happy shoppers	Private (not listed)
12.	Heron Foods	Private (not listed)
13.	Iceland	Private (not listed)
14.	Jack’s	Private (not listed)
15.	Julian graves	Private (not listed)

16.	Lidl	Private (not listed)
17.	Londis	Private (not listed)
18.	Makro	Private (not listed)
19.	Marks & Spencer (M&S)	Private (not listed)
20.	Morrisons	Private (not listed)
21.	Netto	Private (not listed)
22.	Nisa	Private (not listed)
23.	ODDBOX	Private (not listed)
24.	One store	Private (not listed)
25.	Planet organic	Private (not listed)
26.	Premier stores	Private (not listed)
27.	River ford	Private (not listed)
28.	Scotmid	Private (not listed)
29.	SPAR	Private (not listed)
30.	Sprouts farmer market	Private (not listed)
31.	TESCO express	Private (not listed)
32.	The co-operative	Private (not listed)
33.	Waitrose & Partners	Private (not listed)
34.	Whole foods	Private (not listed)
35.	ASDA Plc	Public (Listed)
36.	Ocado Group Plc	Public (Listed)
37.	Sainsbury's Plc	Public (Listed)
38.	Tesco Plc	Public (Listed)

❖ Yougov (2022).

❖ Financial Knowledge & Info Portal, (2022)

3.4.3 Sample Selection Process

The sample selection involved selecting six (6) (listed & non-listed) supermarkets for this study. A stratified sampling technique is required for the sample selection process due to the heterogeneous characteristics of the supermarkets. The population is first divided into strata based on the nature of how the supermarkets operate (London stock exchange status- Plc or Ltd). Afterward, three supermarkets will be randomly selected from each stratum.

3.4.4 Final Sample Selection

The final sample selection involves the selection of six UK supermarkets, (3 listed & 3 non-listed supermarkets). There are thirty-eight (38) supermarket chains situated in the United Kingdom comprising 4 listed supermarkets (public companies) and 34 non-listed supermarkets (private companies). After categorizing them into strata based on their corporate status (private & public companies), a random selection of 3 supermarkets will be drawn from each stratum, reaching an aggregate of 6 supermarket chains. Finally, ASDA, Sainsbury's Plc, and Tesco Plc will be selected as public companies (listed supermarkets), while Booths, Lincolnshire Co-op Food, and Iceland are the private companies selected (non-listed supermarkets).

3.5 Time Horizon

Most research studies that involve time factors are either cross-sectional or longitudinal studies in nature. In cross-sectional designs, data are collected at a single point in time. All measures are taken at the same time to detect patterns of association or changes across time. A cross-sectional design entails the collection of data on more than one case and at a single point in time to collect a body of quantitative or quantifiable data in connection with two or more variables (Bryman, 2012; Robson & McCartan, 2016). However, longitudinal design involves data collection at more than one point in time or a brief period that is data are collected on a variable over time. With a longitudinal design, a sample is surveyed and is surveyed again on at least one further occasion (Bryman, 2012; Robson & McCartan, 2016).

In this study, a cross-sectional design will be adopted to provide information on the impact of the recent corporate governance code on UK supermarket businesses. The recent UK corporate governance code was enacted in 2018 to define how companies are being managed and controlled; it aimed to promote credible standards on board leadership and purpose, board composition, remuneration, nomination and audit committees, and shareholder relations (Mallin, 2019). The study will cover 4 years because the recent UK corporate governance code was enacted in 2018. This period of coverage will last from 2018 to 2021, revealing the compliance of supermarkets with the UK corporate governance code. The time horizon chosen is imperative as it justifies the comparative analysis of listed and non-listed supermarkets' compliance with the UK 2018 code across time.

3.6 Data Analysis

The section of the methodology focuses on how the data to be collected will be analysed to explore the impact of the recent UK corporate governance code on both listed and non-listed supermarkets, showing their trend of compliance in the last 4 years.

3.6.1 Unit of Analysis and Measurement

The study will adopt the use of descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentages, and charts will be used to analyse the data collected, showing the trend of how supermarkets adopt the 2018 UK corporate governance code to promote diversity.

CHAPTER FOUR: ANALYSES AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of data and the discussion of the findings. The analyses were presented to answer the research questions raised to implement the study.

4.1 Analyses

4.1.1 Research Question One: Has the UK corporate governance code promoted gender diversity on the board among listed and non-listed supermarkets when compared to in the last four years?

The result of research question one is analysed in each of the selected supermarkets, and it is analysed as follows:

Figure 4.1 Board Gender Diversity in Booths and Iceland (2018-2021) (non-listed supermarkets)

Source: Table 4.1 (Appendix I)

(Booths Annual Report 2018-2021; Iceland Annual Report 2018-2021)

Figure 4.1 presents the proportion of directors based on their gender diversity from 2018 to 2022 in Booths and Iceland. In the figure, the proportion of male directors in Booths and Iceland showed no gender diversity with males dominating the board (100% representation from 2018 to 2021 respectively). Also, the Hampton-Alexander threshold has not been met by both Booths or Iceland as no women were appointed as board members in both companies.

Figure 4.2 Board Gender Diversity in Lincolnshire Co-op (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.1 (Appendix I)
(Lincolnshire Co-op Annual Report 2018-2021)

Figure 4.2 presents the proportion of directors based on their gender diversity from 2018 to 2022 in Lincolnshire Co-op. The proportion of female directors exceeded the Hampton-Alexander threshold because it is mostly dominated by women (from 2018-2021). Although the male representation increased slightly from 2018 to 2020 (increment from 33% to 44% in 2019; and 45% in 2020) it remained stagnant afterward at 45% representation. Similarly, female representation reduced but remained stagnant afterward.

Figure 4.3 Board Gender Diversity in ASDA Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.1 (Appendix I)

(ASDA Plc Annual Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.3, the proportion of female directors did not meet the Hampton-Alexander threshold from 2018-2021. ASDA Plc constantly reduced its male board representation annually (reduction from 89% to 80% in 2019, 75% in 2020) except for 2021 where it increased (75% to 81% in 2021). Similarly, female representation increased yearly to approach the threshold but remained stagnant afterward, except for 2021. The exception in 2021 was caused by the number of appointments and resignations among the board members (appointments-4 males, 1 female: resignations - 4 males). If the number of board members that resigned was removed, then the status of board representation in the previous year remains (75% of males to 25% of females).

Figure 4.4 Board Gender Diversity in Sainsbury’s Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.1 (Appendix I)
 (Sainsbury’s Plc Annual Report 2018-2021)

Figure 4.4 showed the proportion of gender representation on the board in Sainsbury’s Plc. The board showed a static ratio of men to women (7:3 respectively) on the board from 2018 to 2021. Also, the Hampton-Alexander threshold has not been met because of low women representation which is 30% (3% lower Hampton- Alexander threshold) that were appointed as board members in the company.

Figure 4.5 Board Gender Diversity in TESCO Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.1 (Appendix I)

(Tesco Plc Annual Report 2018-2021)

Finally, Figure 4.5 showed the proportion of gender representation on the board in Tesco Plc. The board showed a movement in women’s board representation towards the threshold in 2019 (21% to 31%) but remained afterward (2020 & 2021). Also, the Hampton- Alexander threshold has not been met because of low women representation which is 31% appointment of female board members in the company.

Overall, the UK corporate governance code has not consistently promoted gender board diversity among most supermarkets, although listed supermarkets showed better efforts to achieve gender board diversity. The non-listed supermarkets had more gender-diverse boards than the listed supermarkets because one of its supermarkets Lincolnshire Co-op (which was dominated by women) had achieved the Hampton-Alexander Review benchmark of 33% women’s board representation. However, no attempt was made by the remaining two supermarkets (Booths & Iceland) to achieve gender-board diversity. Although all the listed supermarkets are moving towards achieving the Hampton-Alexander Review target of 33% women board representation, they stalled or moved farther from the threshold in recent years.

This showed that the UK corporate governance code has not consistently promoted gender board diversity among most of the supermarkets, although listed supermarkets showed better efforts to achieve gender board diversity.

4.1.2 Research Question Two: Has the UK corporate governance promoted the gender pay gap among listed and non-listed supermarkets when compared to in the last four years?

The result of this research question is analysed in each of the selected supermarkets using the mean gender pay gap indices:

Figure 4.6 Mean gender pay gap in Booths (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)
(Booths Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.6, Booths’ mean gender pay gap report showed a curve movement. The gender pay gap was reduced in 2019 (by 3% to 11%), remained static in 2020 but increased (by 5.5% to 16.5%) in 2021.

Figure 4.7 Mean gender pay gap in Iceland (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)
 (Iceland Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.7, Iceland’s mean gender pay gap report showed a fluctuating movement. The gender pay gap increased in 2019 (by 0.3% to 13.5%), reduced in 2020 (by 4.8% to 8.7%) but increased (by 1.5% to 10.2%) in 2021.

Figure 4.8 Mean gender pay gap in Lincolnshire Co-op (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)
 (Lincolnshire Co-op Gender Pay Gap Report 2-18-2021)

In figure 4.8, the Lincolnshire Co-op gender pay gap report showed a decline movement. The gender pay gap initially increased in 2019 (by 4.9% to 26.9%), reduced in 2020 (by 3.1% to 23.8%), and further reduced (by 3.6% to 20.2%) in 2021).

Figure 4.9 Mean gender pay gap in ASDA Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)
(ASDA Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.9, the ASDA gender pay gap report showed a decline movement. The gender pay gap decreased in 2019 (by 1.3% to 11.1%), reduced further in 2020 (by 2.7% to 8.4%) and further reduced (by 0.4% to 8%) in 2021.

Figure 4.10 Mean gender pay gap in Sainsbury’s Plc (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)
 (Sainsbury’s Plc Gender Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.10, Sainsbury’s gender pay gap report showed a decline movement. The gender pay gap decreased in 2019 (by 1.4% to 10.3%), reduced further in 2020 (by 0.7% to 9.6%) and further reduced (by 1.3% to 8.3%) in 2021.

Figure 4.11 Mean gender pay gap in Tesco Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.2 (Appendix II)

In figure 4.10, Tesco’s gender pay gap report showed a decline movement. The gender pay gap initially increased in 2019 (by 1.3% to 12.6%), but later reduced in 2020 (by 2.6% to 10%) and further reduced (by 0.7% to 9.3%) in 2021.

Overall, the listed supermarkets fared better than their non-listed counterparts because they have been consistent in reducing the pay gaps recently. Also, most of the listed supermarkets produced lower pay gaps compared to the non-listed supermarkets. This showed that the UK corporate governance is helpful in reducing the gender pay gap more in listed supermarkets when compared to the non-listed supermarkets.

4.1.3 Research Question Three: Has the UK corporate governance code promoted diversity among employees in listed and non-listed supermarkets when compared to in the last four years?

The result of this research question is analysed in each of the selected supermarkets using the mean gender pay gap indices:

Figure 4.12 Gender Diversity among employees in Booths (non-listed spermarket)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)
(Booths Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.12, gender diversity among employees in Booths showed a fluctuating movement. The number of male employees increased in 2019 (by 2% to 49%), remained static in 2020 but later reduced (by 1% to 48%) in 2021. For the female employees, their numbers decreased in 2019 (by 2% to 51%), remained static in 2020 but later increased (by 1% to 52%) in 2021. In general, there are more female employees in the organisation.

Figure 4.13 Gender Diversity among employees in Iceland (non-listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)
 (Iceland Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.13, gender diversity among employees in Iceland showed a fluctuating movement. The diversity among male employees increased in 2019 (by 1% to 48%), increased further (by 2% to 50%) in 2020 but later reduced (by 1% to 49%) in 2021. Similarly, the number of female employees decreased (by 1% to 52%) in 2019, reduced further in 2020 (by 2% to 50%) but later increased (by 1% to 51%) in 2021. Overall, there are more female employees in the organisation when compared with male employees.

Figure 4.14 Gender Diversity among employees in Lincolnshire Co-op (non-listed spermarket)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)
 (Lincolnshire Co-op Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.14, gender diversity among employees in Lincolnshire Co-op showed a fluctuating movement. The male employee representation decreased (by 3% to 26%) in 2019, increased (by 1% to 27%) in 2020 but later reduced (by 1% to 26%) in 2021. Also, the number of female employees increased (by 3% to 74%) in 2019, reduced further in 2020 (by 1% to 73%) but later increased (by 1% to 74%) in 2021. In general, female employees are more than male employees in Lincolnshire Co-op.

Figure 4.15 Gender Diversity among employees in ASDA Plc (listed spermarket)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)
 (ASDA Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.15, gender diversity among employees in ASDA Plc showed a slow and reduced movement. The diversity among male employees increased in 2019 (by 1% to 44%), remained stagnant in 2020 but increased (by 2% to 46%) in 2021. Moreover, the number of female employees decreased (by 1% to 56%) in 2019, remained stagnant in 2020, and reduced further (by 2% to 54%) in 2021. ASDA Plc has lots of female employees in the organisation when compared with male employees.

Figure 4.16 Gender Diversity among employees in Sainsbury’s Plc (listed supermarket)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)
 (Sainsbury’s Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021)

In figure 4.16, gender diversity among employees in Sainsbury’s Plc showed a slow and reduced movement. The diversity among male employees remained stagnant in 2019, moved towards the threshold through an increase in 2020 (by 3% to 45%), and increased (by 1% to 46%) in 2021.

Moreover, the number of female employees remained stagnant in 2019, but decreased (by 3% to 55%) in 2020 and reduced further (by 1% to 54%) in 2021. Generally, there are more female employees in the organisation when compared with male employees.

Figure 4.17 Gender Diversity among employees in TESCO Plc (listed)

Source: Table 4.3 (Appendix III)

In figure 4.17, gender diversity among employees in TESCO Plc showed a slow and reduced movement. The diversity among male employees increased (by 1% to 44%) in 2019, remained stagnant in 2020, and later moved towards the threshold through an increase in 2021 (by 3% to 47%). Moreover, the number of female employees decreased (by 1% to 56%) in 2019, remained stagnant in 2020, and decreased further (by 3% to 53%) in 2021. Generally, there are more female employees in the organisation when compared with the male employee

Overall, the UK corporate governance code 2018 promoted gender diversity among employees in listed supermarkets but remained inconsistent in its implementation in non-listed supermarkets (Booths and Iceland) except for Lincolnshire Co-op. Lincolnshire Co-op is the only supermarket that has the highest percentage of female employees and has since maintained the standard in the last four years.

To improve gender diversities and reduce gender pay gaps, the several steps taken by the supermarkets are:

	The efforts to reduce gender diversity & gender pay gaps	Supermarkets
1.	Advertise all vacancies	Asda Plc
2.	The flexibility of working place: working from home, office	Asda Plc
3.	Leadership and management development programmes: accelerated development among high-potential female colleagues through both individual and cohort development programmes	Asda Plc, Sainsbury's Plc, Tesco Plc, Booths, Lincolnshire Co-op
4.	Inclusive recruitment policies and practices: Implement new digital recruitment tools to improve candidate experience, increase access to a more diverse range of job boards and widen the pool of applicants	Asda Plc, Tesco Plc, Lincolnshire Co-op
5.	Improved paid maternity or adoption leave, and paternity leave.	Sainsbury's Plc,
6.	Having great policies in place to support working families: to attract and retain great colleagues of all genders, and in particular help female colleagues to make store manager and senior leadership roles work for them more effectively	Sainsbury's Plc, Booths
7.	Visibility of women in the business is key: a regular celebration of female role models at all levels	Asda Plc, Sainsbury's Plc
8.	Helping young people to get on: In addition to permanent roles across the business, apprenticeships, internships, and graduate opportunities are provided	Tesco Plc
9.	Educating and empowering female colleagues	Tesco Plc, Booths ltd, Lincolnshire Co-op

(Booths Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021; Iceland Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021; Lincolnshire Co-op Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021; ASDA Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021; Sainsbury's Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021; Tesco Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021).

From the table above, the listed supermarkets have made more efforts in promoting diversity towards ensuring a balanced board for women and a suitable working environment for its employees, than their counterparts. The efforts made by the listed supermarkets coincide with the data presented in their respective gender pay gap reports.

4.2 Discussion of findings

The findings in the first research question revealed that the 2018 UK corporate governance code has not consistently promoted gender board diversity among most of the supermarkets, although listed supermarkets showed better efforts to achieve gender board diversity. This is promising for listed supermarkets, and this revealed the continued progress towards the Hampton-Alexander Review target of 33% by 2020. Among the non-listed supermarkets, Iceland and Booths did not implement the board gender diversity as stipulated by the UK corporate governance code because they are not listed companies and are not bound by the requirements of the 2018 UK code (UK Corporate Governance Code, 2018), and they both have men as their directors from 2018 to 2021. Also, both Iceland & Booths adopted the Water Governance for large private companies published by the FRC (Iceland Annual Report, 2018-2021 & Booths Annual report 2018 – 2021).

While Lincolnshire Co-op abides by the voluntary code for consumer operatives issued by the Co-operatives UK (Lincolnshire Co-op Annual Report, 2018-2021) and is largely dominated by females. Lincolnshire Co-op has more female board members because more female members participate and vote in the election of board members. Generally, women poll more votes than men during elections. It is important to note that at Lincolnshire Co-op board, directors are usually made up of 12 members, 9 are elected and up to three can be appointed by the elected directors (Lincolnshire Co-op Annual Report, 2018 - 2021).

The importance of diversity is also embedded in the productivity and quality performance of the company because diversity leads to better efficiency, productivity, and quality performance of the company. The study corroborates the reports of Sealy (2018), BRC, PwC & MBS Group (2021), DLA Piper and Green Park (2019), and Irvine et al., (2022) which revealed that businesses in the UK continue to progress towards achieving the Hampton-Alexander Review target of 33% of gender board diversity.

Secondly, the trend of the mean pay gap showed that the 2018 UK corporate governance is effective in reducing the gender pay gap among listed supermarkets when compared to the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years. This result is not impressive on the part of the non-listed supermarkets because the pay gaps are caused by more male employees earning more than their female counterparts and there are more female employees on part-time payroll. Part-time jobs contributed more to the overall pay, where positions are mostly occupied by women. This result corroborates the reports of Brynin (2017), Colebrook *et al.*, (2018), Jewell *et al.*, (2018), CDC (2021), White (2021,) and Irvine et al., (2022).

The 2018 UK corporate governance code promoted gender diversity among employees in listed supermarkets but remained inconsistent in its implementation in the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years. This is also largely due to women dominating the retail markets jobs, part-time jobs contributed more to the overall pay, where positions are mostly occupied by women. However, there is a need for consistency on the part of the non-listed supermarkets to harmonize their practice to reflect the target of the UK corporate governance code 2018. The results support the reports of BRC, PwC & MBS Group (2021), Equileap (2022), and (Irvine et al., (2022). However, it contradicts the reports of Sealy (2018), ILO (2019), ILO (2022), and Zhu (2021) who opined that women are estimated to have lower chances of being employed than men.

Finally, when linking the three outcomes of this study based on the category of supermarkets (i.e., comparing gender board diversity, gender pay gap, and gender employee diversity between listed and non-listed supermarkets), the listed supermarkets implemented the code better than their non-listed counterparts. The listed supermarkets showed a better gender-diverse board and employee gender diversity with the aim of gradual reduction of gender imbalance. This also affected the mean pay gap indices of listed supermarkets because male staff tends to occupy higher positions than women in the organisations.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the summary of findings, contribution and implication of the study, and suggestions for future research.

5.1 Summary of findings

The study is a novel area of investigation which focused on how the 2018 UK corporate governance code promotes gender diversity in the retail market with a special focus on supermarkets. It investigated how the 2018 UK corporate governance code promotes gender diversity on the board, gender pay gap, and diversity among employees between listed and non-listed supermarkets in the United Kingdom in the last four years (2018-2021). The study obtained secondary and quantitative data from the financial statements, gender pay gap reports, websites, and press releases of the selected supermarkets, and the data collected were analysed with descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentages, and charts, showing the trend of how supermarkets adopted the UK corporate governance code 2018 to promote gender diversity on the board, equal gender pay, and diversity among employees.

The result of the first research question revealed that the UK corporate governance code has not consistently promoted gender board diversity among most of the supermarkets, although listed supermarkets showed better efforts to achieve gender board diversity. Secondly, the trend of the mean pay gap showed that the UK corporate governance code 2018 is effective in reducing the gender pay gap among listed supermarkets when compared to the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years. Finally, the UK corporate governance code promoted gender diversity among employees in listed supermarkets but remained inconsistent in its implementation in the non-listed supermarkets in the last four years.

5.2 Contribution and Implication of findings

The study provides insights into how the recent UK corporate governance code impacts the retail industry with a special focus on supermarkets which is a new area of discourse. The findings contribute to the existing literature by providing information on how the recent version of the UK corporate governance code impacts board gender diversity, gender pay gap, and employee gender diversity among supermarkets in the retail industry.

It provides insight for policymakers and other stakeholders in the retail market industry information and status report about the implementation of the UK 2018 code in the last four years. Also, information was provided to reveal the non-implementation of the UK corporate

governance code among non-listed supermarkets over the years, it will also help policymakers to determine the need to review the 2018 UK corporate governance code.

5.3 Limitations of the study

The limitation of the study are constraints that affect the generalisation of the study and problems encountered during data collection. The study was limited to an aggregate of six (6) supermarkets (three listed and non-listed) from the available list of supermarkets in the United Kingdom. This is not the general view as there are other supermarkets in the UK. Another limitation of the study is that no rationale was given as to the appointments of directors on the board of the selected supermarkets. Lastly, the study was limited to only secondary data including financial reports, gender pay gap reports, websites, and press releases of the selected supermarkets. It was difficult to access the board members and managers of the various supermarkets (listed and non-listed) to grant interviews to add more quality to the data collected.

5.4 Suggestions for Future Research

Further studies could be done to investigate other areas of diversity within the supermarkets such as ethnic diversity, and the inclusion of the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) community. In addition, further studies could be done to include primary data collection from the personnel of the supermarkets to obtain in-depth information on how the 2018 UK corporate governance code promotes gender diversity on the board, diversity among employees, and the reduction of gender pay gaps in the supermarkets.

REFERENCES

- Abid, H., (2021). *The Gender Pay Gap in the UK*. Women's Budget Group. Available from: <https://wbg.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Gender-Pay-Gap-briefing.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- ACCA (2018). *Diversifying the board – a step towards better governance*. ACCA Global. Available from: www.accaglobal.com/us/en/student/exam-support-resources/professional-exams-study-resources/strategic-businessleader/technical-articles/diversifying-the-board.html#Definition-of-board-diversity. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Adams, R. B, & Ferreira, D., (2009). *Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2):291–309. Available from: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0304405X09001421?casa_token=AdZ1978sVbQAAAAA:etX6wPg2pNjEw9jIHmNc34XNTE_NZ3Biqd7wCQaPOF2pbCVC5SkLG-sQTKnTHL8JvumO0yjm [Accessed 22 September 2022].
- Arvanitis, S. E., Evangelos G. V., & George, M. A., (2022). *Does Board Gender Diversity Really Improve Firm Performance? Evidence from Greek Listed Firms*. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 15: 306.1-19. Available at <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15070306> [Accessed 22 September 2022].
- Avcin, M., & Balcioglu, H. (2017). *Corporate Governance: A Comparative Study of Firms In Northern Cyprus And Turkey*. *Revista De Cercetare Si Interventie Sociala*, 57(2017), 182-201. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318745663> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- ALHarbi, A. (2018). *An Assessment of the Impact of Corporate Governance Practices on the Values of Firms in the United Kingdom and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: A Comparative Study Using the Ethical Process Thinking Model (EPTM)*. Ph.D. University of Hull. Available from: <https://hydra.hull.ac.uk/assets/hull:17338a/content> [Accessed 12 August 2022].

- ASDA Group (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from: [ASDA GROUP FS 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- ASDA Group (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: [ASDA GROUP FS 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- ASDA Group (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: [ASDA GROUP FS 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- ASDA Group (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: [ASDA GROUP FS 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- ASDA (2018), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2018*. Available from: [ASDA GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- ASDA (2019), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2019*. Available from: [ASDA GROUP FS 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- ASDA (2020), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2020*. Available from: [ASDA GENDER PAY GAP REPORT-2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- ASDA (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: [ASDA GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Avcin, M., & Balcioglu, H. (2017). *Corporate Governance: A Comparative Study of Firms In Northern Cyprus And Turkey*. *Revista De Cercetare Si Interventie Sociala*, 57(2017), 182-201. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318745663> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Bhandari, P., (2018). *Corporate Governance: A Comparative Analysis in India and the US*. Honors. Bryant University. Available from: https://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1018&context=honors_accounting [Accessed 21 June 2022].

- Biswas, P., Chapple, L., Roberts, H., Stainback, K., (2021) *Board Gender Diversity and Women in Senior Management*. Available from: <https://eds-p-ebSCOhost-com.proxy.library.lincoln.ac.uk/eds/detail/detail?vid=6&sid=097ec113-83e7-4825-ad26e57996d20342%40redis&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWRzLWxpdmUmc2NvcGU9c210ZQ%3d%3d#db=edssjs&AN=edssjs.5EB4B25E> [Accessed 18 July 2022].
- Boon, I., (2004) *Board Structure and Firm Performance: Evidence from Australia*. Journal of the Australian and New Zealand, 10(1) 14 - 24. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305981741_Board_Structure_and_Firm_Performance_Evidence_from_Australia [Accessed 13 August 2022].
- British Council (2021). *British Council Gender Pay Gap Report*. Narrative report summary – reporting year 2019/20. Available from: https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/gender_pay_gap_report_2019-20.pdf [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Booths (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from: [BOOTHS FS 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 30 August 2022].
- Booths (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: [BOOTHS FS 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 30 August 2022].
- Booths (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: [BOOTHS FS 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 30 August 2022].
- Booths (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: [BOOTHS FS 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 30 August 2022].
- Booths (2018), *Gender Pay Report 2018*. Available from: [BOOTHS GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Booths (2019), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2019*. Available from: [BOOTHS GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].

- Booths (2020), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2020*. Available from: [BOOTHS GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Booths (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: [BOOTHS GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- BRC, PwC & MBS Group, (2021). *Diversity and Inclusion in UK retail: Where are we now and what comes next?* In-depth research and analysis from BRC, The MBS Group and PwC. MBS Intelligence. Available from: <https://brc.org.uk/media/677267/diversity-and-inclusion-in-uk-retail-in-depth-research-and-analysis-from-brc-the-mbs-group-and-pwc-2021-002.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Burke, R. J. (2000). *Company Size, Board Size, and the Number of Women Directors*. In R. J. Burke and M. C. Mattis (eds), *Women on Corporate Boards of Directors: International Challenges and Opportunities*, 157–167.
- Brown, D., (2019) *Gender Pay Gaps, the UK Experience: How Do We Close Them, How Do We Bring Research Into Practice?* *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 51(4) Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/0886368719895934> [Accessed 25 July 2022].
- Bryman, A., (2012). *Social Research Methods* (4th Ed.). United States: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Brynin, M., (2017). *The gender pay gap*. Equality and Human Rights Commission Research. Report number: 109. Available from: <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/sites/default/files/research-report-109-the-gender-pay-gap.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Carter, B., Simkins, B., Simpson, G., (2003). *Corporate Governance, Board Diversity and Firm Value*. *Research gate Publications*. 38(1): 33- 53. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228292359_Corporate_Governance_Board_Diversity_and_Firm_Performance [Accessed 18 July 2022].

- Cassell, C., Watson, K., Ford, J. & Kele, J. (2022). *Understanding inclusion in the retail industry: Incorporating the majority perspective*. *Personnel Review*, 51 (1). 230-250. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-02-2020-0083>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- CDC (2021). *Gender and Ethnicity Pay Gap Report*. CDC, the UK's development finance institution. Available from: <https://assets.cdcgroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/12162310/Gender-Pay-Gap-Report-2021.pdf>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (2022). *Inclusion and diversity in the workplace*. Available from: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/fundamentals/relations/diversity/factsheet> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Chaudhry, I. S., Paquibut, R. Y., Tunio, M, N., (2021). *Do workforce diversity, inclusion practices, & organizational characteristics contribute to organizational innovation? Evidence from the UAE*. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1-24. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23311975.2021.1947549> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Close The Gap Working Paper (2022). *Gender Pay Gap Statistics*. Available from: <https://www.closesthegap.org.uk/content/resources/Gender-pay-gap-statistics-paper-2022.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Colebrook, C., Snelling, C., & Longlands, S., (2018). *The state of pay: Demystifying the gender pay gap*. Institute for Public Policy Research. Available from: <https://www.ippr.org/files/2018-05/state-of-pay-may18.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th ed.). United States: Sage publication.
- Darmadi, S., (2011) *Board diversity and Firm Performance. The Indonesian Evidence*. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 9 (1) 524 – 539. Available from :

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228240192_Board_Diversity_and_Firm_Performance_The_Indonesian_Evidence [Accessed 13 August 2022].

- DLA Piper & Green Park (2019). *A review of the diversity composition of leading retail board across the UK, US and Europe*. The retail leadership 700. Available from: <https://dlapiper.com/~media/file/insights/publications/2019/06/the-retail-leadership-700.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Eklund, J., Palmberg, J., Wilberg, D., (2009) *Ownership Structure, Board Composition and Investment Performance*. CESIS Electronic Working Paper Series Paper No:17. Available from : https://www.researchgate.net/publication/24008219_Ownership_Structure_Board_Composition_and_Investment_Performance [Accessed 13 August 2022].
- Equileap (2022). *Gender Equality Global Report & Ranking, 2022 Edition*. Available from: https://equileap.com/wpcontent/uploads/2022/03/Equileap_Global_Report_2022.pdf [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Faccio, M., Marchica. M-T., & Mura, R., (2016). *CEO gender, corporate risk-taking, and the efficiency of capital allocation*. *Journal of Corporate Finance* 39:193–209. Available from: https://www.research.manchester.ac.uk/portal/files/45984177/CEO_gender_02222016.pdf [Accessed 21 September 2022].
- Farrell, K.A., Hersh, P.L., (2005) *Additions to Corporate Boards: The Effect of Gender*. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 11 (1-2) 85 – 206. Available from : [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222574136_Additions_to_Corporate_Boards_The_Effect_of_Gender#:~:text=For%20example%2C%20Farrell%20and%20Hersch%20\(2005\)%20show%20that%20board,a%20majority%20of%20men%20directors](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222574136_Additions_to_Corporate_Boards_The_Effect_of_Gender#:~:text=For%20example%2C%20Farrell%20and%20Hersch%20(2005)%20show%20that%20board,a%20majority%20of%20men%20directors) [Accessed 13 August 2022].
- Financial Conduct Authority (2015). *Co-operative and Community Benefit Societies Act 2014*. [online] Available at: <https://www.fca.org.uk/firms/registered-societies->

[introduction/co-operative-community-benefit-societies-act-2014](#) [Accessed 25 August 2022].

- Financial Reporting Council, (2018). The UK Corporate Governance Code 2018. pp. 1-15. Available from: [2018-UK-Corporate-Governance-Code-FINAL.pdf](#) [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Financial Knowledge & Info Portal, (2022). Drug and grocery stores stock list UK, 2022. Available from: <http://fknol.com/uk/stock/drug-and-grocery-stores.php> [Accessed 19 July 2022].
- Garcia-Meca, E., & Santana-Martín, D. J., (2022). *Board gender diversity and performance in family firms: exploring the fault line of family ties*. Review of Managerial Science. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11846-022-00563-3> [Accessed 21 September 2022].
- Gantner, O. (2020). *Closing Gender Pay Gaps To Achieve Gender Equality At Work*. Womens' Empowerment principle. Available from: https://www.weps.org/sites/default/files/2020-04/Equal%20Pay%20Guidance%20Note_Final.pdf [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Goyal, R., Kakabadse, N., Kakabadse, A., (2019). *Improving Corporate Governance with functional diversity on FTSE 350 boards: directors' perspective*. Journal of Capital Market Studies, 3(2) 113 -136. Available from <https://eds.p.ebscohost.com/eds/detail/detail?vid=7&sid=7e978b2d-afbc-4f2c-a5764c212c85e5d%40redis&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWRzLWxpdmUmc2NvcGU9c210ZQ%3d%3d#AN=edsemr.10.1108.JCMS.09.2019.0044&db=edsemr> [Accessed 18 July 2022].
- Gov.uk (2020). *Gender pay gap reporting*. GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/gender-pay-gap-reporting> (Accessed 13 July 2022).

- Harvard Business Review Analytic Services (2021). *Creating a Culture of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion: Real Progress Requires Sustained Commitment*. Available from: <https://hbr.org/sponsored/2021/09/creating-a-culture-of-diversity-equity-and-inclusion>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Hosny, K., & Elgharbawy, A. (2021). *Board diversity and financial performance: empirical evidence from the United Kingdom*. *Accounting Research Journal*, 35(4): 1-8. Available from: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/1030-9616/vol35/iss/4> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Iceland (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from: [ICELAND FS 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: [ICELAND FS 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: [ICELAND FS 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: [ICELAND FS 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2019), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2019*. Available from: <https://about.iceland.co.uk/gender-pay-gap-report-2019/> [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2020), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2020*. Available from: <https://about.iceland.co.uk/great-place-to-work/gender-pay-gap-report/> [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Iceland (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: <https://gender-pay-gap.service.gov.uk/Employer/kGuVNcCv/2021> [Accessed 4 September 2022].

- ILO, (2019). *A Quantum Leap for Gender Equality: For a Better Future of Work For All*. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_674831/lang-en/index.htm. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- International Trade Union Confederation, (2018). *ITUC Economic and Social Policy Brief: The Gender Wage Gap*. Available from: https://www.ituc-csi.org/IMG/pdf/the_gender_wage_gap_en.pdf. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- International Labour Organization, (2020). *Empowering Women at Work – Company Policies and Practices for Gender Equality*. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/goups/public/-ed_emp/--emp_ent/--multi/documents/publication/wcms_773233.pdf [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- International Labour Organization, (2022). *Transforming enterprises through diversity and inclusion*. Available from: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/goups/public/-ed_emp/--emp_ent/--multi/documents/publication/wcms_773233.pdf. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Irvine, S., Clark, H., Ward, M., & Francis-Devine, B. (2022). *Women and the UK Economy*. Commons Library Research Briefing. Research Number 6838. Available from: <https://commonlibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn0638/>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Jewell, S.L, Razzu, G., Singleton, C., (2018). *Who works for whom and the UK gender pay gap*. Edinburgh School of Economics Discussion Paper Series. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324904976_Who_Works_for_Whom_and_the_UK_Gender_Pay_Gap [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Kang, K., Cheng, M., Gray, C.S., (2007) *Corporate Governance and Board Composition: diversity and independence of Australian boards*. Wiley Online Library, 15(2). Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2007.00554.x> [Accessed 12 August 2022].

- Leaker, D., (2008) *Economic & Labour Market Review Contents*. Office for National Statistics. 2(4). Available from : <https://escoe-website.s3.amazonaws.com/wpcontent/uploads/2020/09/04202706/Economic-Labour-Market-Review-April-2008.pdf#page=19> [Accessed 28 July 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP FS 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP FS 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP FS 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP FS 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2018), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2018*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2018.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2019), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2019*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2020), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2020*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Lincolnshire Co-operative (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: [LINCOLNSHIRE CO-OP GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].

- Lord Davies Review (2011) *Women on Boards*. Available from : [https://www.womenonboards.net/getattachment/Resources/Key-External-Reports/Test-\(2\)/2011-Lord-Davies-review-women-on-ftse-boards.pdf.aspx?lang=en-AU](https://www.womenonboards.net/getattachment/Resources/Key-External-Reports/Test-(2)/2011-Lord-Davies-review-women-on-ftse-boards.pdf.aspx?lang=en-AU) [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- L'Huillier, B. M. (2014). What does "corporate governance" Actually mean? *Corporate Governance*, 14(3), 300-319. Available from: [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(czeh2tfqyw2orz553k1w0r45\)\)/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=2153638](https://www.scirp.org/(S(czeh2tfqyw2orz553k1w0r45))/reference/ReferencesPapers.aspx?ReferenceID=2153638) [Accessed 12 August 2022].
- Mallin, C., (2019). *Corporate Governance*, 6th Edition Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- MBS Group, IGD and PWC, (2019). *Diversity in Food and Grocery*. 2019 Edition: Available from: <https://www.thembsgroup.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/397402-MBS-Group-%E2%80%93-Diversity-in-Grocery-Bronchure.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- McElhaney, K. & Smith, G., (2017). *Eliminating the Pay Gap: An Exploration of Gender Equality, Equal Pay, and A Company that Is Leading the Way*. Available from : <https://www.icrw.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Eliminating-the-Pay-Gap-Kellie-McElhaney-and-Genevieve-Smith.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Miller, K., Vagins DJ., Hedgepeth, A., Nielson, K., & Nelson, R., (2018). *The Simple truth about the gender pay gap: Fall 2018 edition*. AAUW. Available from : <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Simple-Truth-about-the-Gender-Pay-Gap.-Fall-Miller-Vagins/c670a161acc99cf02c3283b93f5e87ca6ec64dfc> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Moore, K., Xiong, S., Bhattacharya, M., Bustamante, G., Calvert, C., (2020). *Beyond Diversity: Focusing on and Enhancing Inclusion in the Society for Epidemiologic Research*. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 189(10). Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7666410/> [Accessed 1 August 2022].

- Moyser, M., (2019). *Measuring and Analysing the Gender Pay Gap: A Conceptual and Methodological Overview*. Studies on Gender and Intersecting Identities. Available from : https://epe.lac-bac.gc.ca/100/201/301/weekly_acquisitions_list-ef/2019/19-35/publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2019/statcan/452000022019001-eng.pdf [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- National Education Union (2019). *Equal pay and The Equal Pay Act 1970*. NEU. Available from: <https://neu.org.uk/advice/equal-pay-and-equal-pay-act-1970> [Accessed 26 July 2022]
- Nuria, R. A., Joaquina, L. B., Pilar, D. F. R., (2011). Gender diversity on Boards of Directors and business success. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 8(1-1) Available from: https://www.businessperspectives.org/images/pdf/applications/publishing/templates/article/assets/3868/imfi_en_2011_01c_Alvarado.pdf [Accessed 20 September 2022].
- Patton, M. Q., (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (2nd ed.). United States: Sage publication.
- PWC (2021). Step by Step: Closing the retail gap. Gender pay gap in the retail interim report 2020/2021. Available at <https://www.pwc.co.uk/human-resource-services/assets/pdfs/gender-pay-gap-in-retail-sector-2021.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Randoy , T., Oxelheim , L., (2006) *A Nordic perspective on corporate board diversity*. Available from: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:707100/FULLTEXT02> [Accessed 18 July 2022].
- Robson, C., & McCartan, K., (2016). *Real World Research: A Resource for Users of Social Research Methods in Applied Settings*, (4th ed.). Italy: Printer Trento.
- Rohwerder, B. (2017). *Diversity and inclusion within organisations*. K4D Helpdesk Report. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies. Available from: <https://opendocs.ids.ac.uk/opendocs/handle/20.500.12413/13073> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

- Sanni, M. (2015). Corporate Governance in Africa: Comparative Study. Master's thesis at the Aalto University School of Business, Finland. Available from: <https://cor.ac.uk/download/pdf/80717238.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from : https://www.about.sainsburys.co.uk/~/_media/Files/S/Sainsburys/documents/reports-and-presentations/annual-reports/sainsburys-ar-2018-full-report-v2.pdf [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: <https://www.about.sainsburys.co.uk/investors/results-reports-and-presentations/2019> [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: <https://www.about.sainsburys.co.uk/investors/results-reports-and-presentations/2020> [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: <https://about.sainsburys.co.uk/investors/results-reports-and-presentations/2021> [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2018), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2018*. Available from: <file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/ASDA/ASDA%20GENDER%20PAY%20GAP%20REPORT%202021.pdf> [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2019), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2019*. : [SAINSBURY'S GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2019.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2020), *Gender Pay Report 2020*. Available from: [SAINSBURY'S GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Sainsbury's (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: [SAINSBURY'S GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].

- Sanni, M. (2015). Corporate Governance in Africa: Comparative Study. Master's thesis at the Aalto University School of Business, Finland. Available from: <https://cor.ac.uk/download/pdf/80717238.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Sealy. R., (2018). *Board Diversity Reporting*, Financial Reporting Council. Available from: <https://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment/62202e7d-064c-402bd19f9ac9591fe19/Board-Diversity-reporting-september-2018.pdf>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Şener, I. and Karaye, A. (2014). *Board Composition and Gender Diversity: Comparison of Turkish and Nigerian Listed Companies*. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 150, pp.1002–1011. Available from : <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S1877042814051611?token=00EACF61306DE97A2B084690A9697849A288C6633BBCD2672D3AE8A46E0265CA8EA85A283F9757369DE90EADBCFD201B&originRegion=eu-west-1&originCreation=20220812114511> [Accessed 12 August 2022].
- Shore, L., Cleveland, J. N., & Sanchez, D. (2018). Inclusive workplaces: A review and model. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28: 176–189. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318770988_Inclusive_workplaces_A_review_and_model. [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Smith, N., Smith, V., Verner, M., Do Women in top management affect firm performance? A panel of study of 2,500 Danish Firms. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 55(5) 569 – 593. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5161013_Do_Women_in_Top_Management_Affect_Firm_Performance_A_Panel_Study_of_2500_Danish_Firms [Accessed 13 August 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2018), *Annual Report 2018*. Available from: <https://www.tescopl.com/media/755654/b-tesco-2018-annual-report-and-accounts.pdf> [Accessed 24 August 2022].

- Tesco Plc (2019), *Annual Report 2019*. Available from: https://www.tescopl.com/media/476423/tesco_ar_2019.pdf [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2020), *Annual Report 2020*. Available from: https://www.tescopl.com/media/755761/tes006_ar2020_web_updated_200505.pdf [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2021), *Annual Report 2021*. Available from: https://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReports/PDF/LSE_TSCO_2021.pdf [Accessed 24 August 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2018/19), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2018/19*. Available from: [TESCO GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2018-19.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2020), *Gender Pay Report 2020*. Available from: [TESCO GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2020.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Tesco Plc (2021), *Gender Pay Gap Report 2021*. Available from: [TESCO GENDER PAY GAP REPORT 2021.pdf](#) [Accessed 4 September 2022].
- Thomas, J.R., Nelson, J.K., (2001). *Research Methods in Physical Activities* (4th edition). United States: Human Kinetics Publisher, Champaign, IL.
- Vintila, G., Moscu, R. G. (2015). *Comparative analysis regarding the principles contained in the corporate governance code in Romania and other codes of emerging markets*. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*, 7(2015), 89-97.
- White, J. N., (2021). *Gender pay gap in the UK: 2021. Differences in pay between women and men by age, region, full-time and part-time, and occupation*. Statistical bulletin of the Office for National statistics. Available from : <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/earningsandworkinghours/bulletins/genderpaygapintheuk/2021>. [Accessed 21 June 2022].

- Yougov (2022). *List of most popular Supermarket chains* (Q2, 2022). Available from: <http://Yougov.co.uk/ratings/food/popularity/supermarket-chain/all> [Accessed 19 July 2022].
- United Kingdom *Corporate Governance Code 2018* [2018-UK-Corporate-Governance-Code-FINAL.pdf](#) [Accessed 6 October 2021]
- Urwin, P., Parry, E., Dodds, I., Karuk, V., & David, A. (2013). *The Business Case for Equality and Diversity: a survey of the academic literature*. (BIS Occasional Paper No. 4). Department for Business Innovation & Skills & Government Equalities Office. Available from : https://www.academic..edu/35132220/impact_of_diversity_and_inclusion_within_org_anisation [Accessed 21 June 2022].
- Zhu., Z., (2021). *The Causes and Solutions of Gender Inequality in the Workplace*. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 615:693-697. Available from: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/125967127.pdf> [Accessed 21 June 2022].

APPENDIX I

GENDER BOARD DIVERSITY

Table 4.1 Gender Diversity on The Board (2018-2021)

Year	Non-listed					Listed				
	Supermarkets	Gender				Supermarkets	Gender			
		M	%	F	%		M	%	F	%
2018	Booths	8	100	0	0	ASDA Plc	8	89	1	11
	Iceland	3	100	0	0	Sainsbury's Plc	7	70	3	30
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	3	33	6	67	Tesco Plc	10	77	3	23
2019	Booths	6	100	0	0	ASDA Plc	8	80	2	20
	Iceland	4	100	0	0	Sainsbury's Plc	7	70	3	30
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	4	44	5	56	Tesco Plc	9	69	4	31
2020	Booths	6	100	0	0	ASDA Plc	6	75	2	25
	Iceland	6	100	0	0	Sainsbury's Plc	7	70	3	30
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	5	45	6	55	Tesco Plc	9	69	4	31
2021	Booths	5	100	0	0	ASDA Plc	9	81	2	19
	Iceland	5	100	0	0	Sainsbury's Plc	7	70	3	30
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	5	45	6	55	Tesco Plc	9	69	4	31

➤ **Note:** M- Male Board Members; F- Female Board Members; %- Percentages

➤ **Benchmark:** Hampton-Alexander Review target of 33% women by the end of 2020

➤ **Source:**

- ASDA Plc Annual Report 2018-2021.
- Sainsbury's Plc Annual Report 2018-2021.
- Tesco Plc Annual Report 2018-2021
- Booths Annual Report 2018-2021.
- Iceland Annual Report 2018-2021.
- Lincolnshire Co-op Annual Report 2018-2021.

APPENDIX II

GENDER PAY GAP REPORT

Table 4.2 Gender Pay Gap (hourly pay gap) (2018-2021)

Supermarkets		Mean Pay Gap (%)			
		2018	2019	2020	2021
Non-listed	Booths	14	11	11	16.5
	Iceland	13.2	13.5	8.7	10.2
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	22	26.9	23.8	20.2
Listed	ASDA Plc	12.4	11.1	8.4	8
	Sainsbury Plc	11.7	10.3	9.6	8.3
	Tesco Plc	11.3	12.6	10	9.3

➤ **Source:**

- ASDA Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Sainsbury's Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Tesco Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Booths Gender Pay Gap Report 2018 – 2021.
- Iceland Gender Pay Gap Report 2018 – 2021.
- Lincolnshire Co-op Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.

APPENDIX III

GENDER DIVERSITY AMONG EMPLOYEES

Table 4.3 Gender Diversity Among Employees

Year	Non-listed Supermarkets					Listed Supermarkets				
	Supermarkets	Gender				Supermarkets	Gender			
		M	%	F	%		M	%	F	%
2018	Booths	1162	47	1311	53	ASDA Plc	41900	43	55541	57
	Iceland	11150	47	12574	53	Sainsbury's Plc	78754	42	108146	58
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	822	29	2010	71	Tesco Plc	189097	43	251561	57
2019	Booths	1438	49	1497	51	ASDA Plc	41446	44	52749	56
	Iceland	11773	48	12755	52	Sainsbury's Plc	75184	42	104716	58
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	729	26	2076	74	Tesco Plc	199133	44	255286	56
2020	Booths	1507	49	1569	51	ASDA Plc	40104	44	51041	56
	Iceland	12321	50	12321	50	Sainsbury's Plc	77130	45	94270	55
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	775	27	2098	73	Tesco Plc	180186	44	225320	56
2021	Booths	1453	48	1574	52	ASDA Plc	42231	46	49576	54
	Iceland	14825	49	15431	51	Sainsbury's Plc	82800	46	97200	54
	Lincolnshire Co-op Food	756	26	2153	74	Tesco Plc	169852	47	191919	53

➤ **Note:** M- Male Board Members; F- Female Board Members; %- Percentages

➤ **Benchmark:** 50% or equal employee gender representation

➤ **Source:**

- ASDA Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Sainsbury's Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Tesco Plc Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Booths Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.

- Iceland Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.
- Lincolnshire Co-op Gender Pay Gap Report 2018-2021.